

L versus NP

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Abstract

P versus NP is considered as one of the most important open problems in computer science. This consists in knowing the answer of the following question: Is P equal to NP? It was essentially mentioned in 1955 from a letter written by John Nash to the United States National Security Agency. However, a precise statement of the P versus NP problem was introduced independently by Stephen Cook and Leonid Levin. Since that date, all efforts to find a proof for this problem have failed. Another major complexity classes are L and NL. Whether $L = NL$ is another fundamental question that it is as important as it is unresolved. Many computer scientists believe that the problem L versus NP is easier to solve than P versus NP. However, we prove that $L = NL$ if and only if $L = NP$. In this way, we conclude that a proof for a separation of the complexity classes L and NP is so hard to find as proving that L is not equal to NL.

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1 Introduction

In 1936, Turing developed his theoretical computational model [9]. The deterministic and nondeterministic Turing machines have become in two of the most important definitions related to this theoretical model for computation [9]. A deterministic Turing machine has only one next action for each step defined in its program or transition function [9]. A nondeterministic Turing machine could contain more than one action defined for each step of its program, where this one is no longer a function, but a relation [9].

Let Σ be a finite alphabet with at least two elements, and let Σ^* be the set of finite strings over Σ [2]. A Turing machine M has an associated input alphabet Σ [2]. For each string w in Σ^* there is a computation associated with M on input w [2]. We say that M accepts w if this computation terminates in the accepting state, that is $M(w) = \text{“yes”}$ [2]. Note that M fails to accept w either if this computation ends in the rejecting state, that is $M(w) = \text{“no”}$, or if the computation fails to terminate, or the computation ends in the halting state with some output, that is $M(w) = y$ (when M outputs the string y on the input w) [2].

Another relevant advance in the last century has been the definition of a complexity class. A language over an alphabet is any set of strings made up of symbols from that alphabet [4]. A complexity class is a set of problems, which are represented as a language, grouped by measures such as the running time, memory, etc [4]. The language accepted by a Turing machine M , denoted $L(M)$, has an associated alphabet Σ and is defined by:

$$L(M) = \{w \in \Sigma^* : M(w) = \text{“yes”}\}.$$

Moreover, $L(M)$ is decided by M , when $w \notin L(M)$ if and only if $M(w) = \text{“no”}$ [4]. We denote by $t_M(w)$ the number of steps in the computation of M on input w [2]. For $n \in \mathbb{N}$ we denote by $T_M(n)$ the worst case run time of M ; that is:

$$T_M(n) = \max\{t_M(w) : w \in \Sigma^n\}$$

where Σ^n is the set of all strings over Σ of length n [2]. We say that M runs in polynomial time if there is a constant k such that for all n , $T_M(n) \leq n^k + k$ [2]. In other words, this means the language $L(M)$ can be decided by the Turing machine M in polynomial time. Therefore, P is the complexity class of languages that can be decided by deterministic Turing machines in polynomial time [4]. A verifier for a language L_1 is a deterministic Turing machine M , where:

$$L_1 = \{w : M(w, c) = \text{“yes” for some string } c\}.$$

We measure the time of a verifier only in terms of the length of w , so a polynomial time verifier runs in polynomial time in the length of w [2]. A verifier uses additional information, represented by the symbol c , to verify that a string w is a member of L_1 . This information is called certificate. NP is the complexity class of languages defined by polynomial time verifiers [8]. If NP is the class of problems that have succinct certificates, then the complexity class $coNP$ must contain those problems that have succinct disqualifications [8]. That is, a “no” instance of a problem in $coNP$ possesses a short proof of its being a “no” instance [8].

It is fully expected that $P \neq NP$ [8]. Indeed, if $P = NP$ then there are stunning practical consequences [8]. For that reason, $P = NP$ is considered as a very unlikely event [8]. Certainly, P versus NP is one of the greatest open problems in science and a correct solution for this incognita will have a great impact not only in computer science, but for many other fields as well [3]. Whether $P = NP$ or not is still a controversial and unsolved problem [1]. We show some results that could help us to understand better this outstanding problem.

1.1 The Hypothesis

A function $f : \Sigma^* \rightarrow \Sigma^*$ is a polynomial time computable function if some deterministic Turing machine M , on every input w , halts in polynomial time with just $f(w)$ on its tape [9]. Let $\{0, 1\}^*$ be the infinite set of binary strings, we say that a language $L_1 \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$ is polynomial time reducible to a language $L_2 \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$, written $L_1 \leq_p L_2$, if there is a polynomial time computable function $f : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \{0, 1\}^*$ such that for all $x \in \{0, 1\}^*$:

$$x \in L_1 \text{ if and only if } f(x) \in L_2.$$

An important complexity class is NP -complete [5]. If L_1 is a language such that $L' \leq_p L_1$ for some $L' \in NP$ -complete, then L_1 is NP -hard [4]. Moreover, if $L_1 \in NP$, then $L_1 \in NP$ -complete [4]. A principal NP -complete problem is SAT [5]. An instance of SAT is a Boolean formula ϕ which is composed of:

1. Boolean variables: x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n ;
2. Boolean connectives: Any Boolean function with one or two inputs and one output, such as \wedge (AND), \vee (OR), \neg (NOT), \Rightarrow (implication), \Leftrightarrow (if and only if);
3. and parentheses.

A truth assignment for a Boolean formula ϕ is a set of values for the variables in ϕ . A satisfying truth assignment is a truth assignment that causes ϕ to be evaluated as true. A Boolean formula with a satisfying truth assignment is satisfiable. The problem SAT asks whether a given Boolean formula is satisfiable [5]. We define a CNF Boolean formula using the following terms:

A literal in a Boolean formula is an occurrence of a variable or its negation [4]. A Boolean formula is in conjunctive normal form, or CNF , if it is expressed as an AND of clauses, each

of which is the OR of one or more literals [4]. A Boolean formula is in 3-conjunctive normal form or *3CNF*, if each clause has exactly three distinct literals [4]. For example, the Boolean formula:

$$(x_1 \vee \neg x_1 \vee \neg x_2) \wedge (x_3 \vee x_2 \vee x_4) \wedge (\neg x_1 \vee \neg x_3 \vee \neg x_4)$$

is in *3CNF*. The first of its three clauses is $(x_1 \vee \neg x_1 \vee \neg x_2)$, which contains the three literals x_1 , $\neg x_1$, and $\neg x_2$.

A logarithmic space Turing machine has a read-only input tape, a write-only output tape, and read/write work tapes [9]. The work tapes may contain at most $O(\log n)$ symbols [9]. In computational complexity theory, L is the complexity class containing those decision problems that can be decided by a deterministic logarithmic space Turing machine [8]. NL is the complexity class containing the decision problems that can be decided by a nondeterministic logarithmic space Turing machine [8]. The complexity class $coNL$ can be defined as the set of languages such that every element inside of the language will be accepted for every possible path by a nondeterministic logarithmic space Turing machine [8].

The two-way Turing machines may move their head on the input tape into two-way (left and right directions) while the one-way Turing machines are not allowed to move the input head on the input tape to the left [7]. Hartmanis and Mahaney have investigated the classes $1L$ and $1NL$ of languages recognizable by deterministic one-way logarithmic space Turing machine and nondeterministic one-way logarithmic space Turing machine, respectively [6]. They have shown that $1L \neq 1NL$ (by looking at a uniform variant of the string non-equality problem from communication complexity theory) and have defined a natural complete problem for $1NL$ under deterministic one-way logarithmic space reductions [6]. Furthermore, they have proven that $1NL \subseteq L$ if and only if $L = NL$ [6].

Another important complexity class is *coNP-complete* [5]. A principal *coNP-complete* problems is *UNSAT* [5]. A Boolean formula without any satisfying truth assignment is unsatisfiable. The problem *UNSAT* asks whether a given Boolean formula is unsatisfiable [5]. $coNL$ is the complexity class containing the languages such that their complements belong to NL [8]. We can give a disqualification-based definition for $coNL$ [2]. The disqualification-based definition of $coNL$ assumes that a logarithmic space Turing machine has another separated read-only tape, that is the same kind of special tape called “read-once” that we use in the certificate-based definition for NL [2]. Besides, in the disqualification-based definition of $coNL$, we assume the disqualification string is appropriated for the instance [8].

► **Definition 1.** *A language L_1 is in $coNL$ if there exists a deterministic logarithmic space Turing machine M with an additional special read-once input tape polynomial $p : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ such that for every $x \in \{0, 1\}^*$:*

$$x \in L_1 \Leftrightarrow \forall \text{ appropriated } u \in \{0, 1\}^{p(|x|)} \text{ then } M(x, u) = \text{“yes”}$$

where by $M(x, u)$ we denote the computation of M where x is placed on its input tape and the disqualification string u is placed on its special read-once tape, and M uses at most $O(\log |x|)$ space on its read/write tapes for every input x where $|\dots|$ is the bit-length function. We call M as a logarithmic space disqualifier.

For example, there is a well-known $coNL$ problem that states: Given a directed graph $G = (V, E)$ and two nodes $s, t \in V$, is there no possible path from s to t ? In that problem, an appropriated disqualification string u is a sequence of nodes contained in V when s is the first node and t is the last one such that this sequence of nodes is not a path: There is at least a consecutive pair of nodes in the sequence which are not connected by an edge.

We state the following Hypothesis:

► **Hypothesis 1.** *Given a nonempty language $L_1 \in 1NL$, there is a language L_2 in $coNP$ -complete under logarithmic space reductions with a deterministic Turing machine M , where:*

$$L_2 = \{w : M(w, u) = y, \forall \text{ appropriated } u \text{ such that } y \in L_1\}$$

when M runs in logarithmic space in the length of w , u is placed on the special read-once tape of M , and u is polynomially bounded by w . In this way, there is a $coNP$ -complete language defined by a logarithmic space disqualifier M such that when the input is an element of the language with any of its appropriated disqualification, then M always outputs a string which belongs to a single language in $1NL$.

2 Results

We define a well-known $coNP$ -complete problem:

► **Definition 2.** *3UNSAT*

INSTANCE: A Boolean formula ϕ in 3CNF.

QUESTION: Is ϕ unsatisfiable?

REMARKS: 3UNSAT $\in coNP$ -complete [5].

► **Theorem 3.** *If the Hypothesis 1 is true for $L_2 = 3UNSAT$, then $L = NL$ if and only if $L = NP$.*

Proof. We can simulate the computation $M(w, u) = y$ in the Hypothesis 1 by a nondeterministic logarithmic space Turing machine N such that $N(w) = y$, since we can read the certificate string u within the read-once tape by a work tape in a nondeterministic logarithmic space generation of symbols contained in u [8]. Certainly, we can simulate the reading of one symbol from the string u into the read-once tape just nondeterministically generating the same symbol in the work tapes using a logarithmic space [8]. We remove each symbol generated in the work tapes, when we try to generate the next symbol contiguous to the right on the string u . In this way, the generation will always be in logarithmic space. In addition, we can guarantee that the generation of symbols in the work tapes always produces an appropriated string u , since we can check this by symbol per symbol from the generated string u and could make a logarithm space backtracking from the generation in any case.

Under the assumption that $L = NL$, then this nondeterministic logarithmic space Turing machine N can be simulated by a deterministic logarithmic space Turing machine M' . Note that, the nondeterministic logarithmic space Turing machine N with multiple outputs y on w collapses to a single output y' on w under the deterministic logarithmic space Turing machine version M' of N . Moreover, the language $L_1 \in 1NL$ can be decided by a deterministic logarithmic space Turing machine M'' since $1NL \subseteq L$ if and only if $L = NL$ [6]. Finally, we compose the computation as $M''(M'(w))$ in a deterministic logarithmic space computation since L is closed under composition in deterministic logarithmic space [8]. The complexity class $coNL$ contains those languages such that every element in the language will be accepted for every possible path by a nondeterministic logarithmic space Turing machine [8]. The Turing machine that represents the computation of $M''(M'(w))$ will accept every element $w \in 3UNSAT$ for every possible path by a nondeterministic logarithmic space Turing machine since we know that a deterministic computation is also a nondeterministic.

Hence, we deduce that $3UNSAT \in coNL$ if the Hypothesis 1 is true and $L = NL$. In this way, we have that $3UNSAT \in L$ under the assumption of $L = NL$ because of $coNL$ would

collapse to L . Every $coNP$ -complete is logarithmic space reduced to $3UNSAT$. Certainly, every $coNP$ problem could be logarithmic space reduced to $3UNSAT$ by the Cook's Theorem algorithm [5]. Consequently, every language $L_3 \in coNP$ will be in L when the Hypothesis 1 is true for $L_2 = 3UNSAT$ and $L = NL$. Due to we know that P is closed under complement, then we obtain that $L = NP$ [8]. The reverse implication in the other direction, it is easy to deduce since $L = NL$ is trivially true when $L = NP$ (it is not necessary the veracity of the Hypothesis 1 for this implication). ◀

We define a new problem:

► **Definition 4. SUM ZERO**

INSTANCE: A collection of integers C such that $0 \notin C$ and every integer in C has the same bit-length that is equal to the bit-length of the number that is the cardinality of C multiplied by 3 (we do not take into account the symbol minus in counting the bit-length of the negative integers).

QUESTION: Are there two elements $a, b \in C$, such that $a + b = 0$?

REMARKS: We denote this problem as $0SUM$.

► **Theorem 5.** $0SUM \in 1NL$.

Proof. Given a collection of integers C , we can read its elements from left to right, verify that every element is not equal to 0, check that every element in C has the same bit-length and count the amount of elements in C to finally multiply it by 3 and compare the bit-length of this number by the single bit-length from the elements in C . In addition, we can nondeterministically pick two elements a and b from C and accept in case of $a + b = 0$ otherwise we reject. We can make all this computation in a nondeterministic one-way using logarithmic space. Certainly, the calculation and store of the bit-length of the elements in C could be done in logarithmic space since this is a unique value. On the one hand, we can count and store the number of elements that we read from the input and multiply it by 3 to finally compare the bit-length of this number by the stored unique bit-length from the elements of the collection, since the cardinality of C multiplied by 3 could be stored in a binary number of bit-length that is logarithmic in relation to the binary encoded length of C . On the other hand, the two elements a and b that we pick from C have a logarithmic space in relation to the encoded length of C , because of every integer in C has the same bit-length which is equal to the bit-length of the number that is the cardinality of C multiplied by 3. Indeed, we never need to read to the left on the input for the acceptance of the elements in $0SUM$ in a nondeterministic logarithmic space. ◀

► **Theorem 6.** *There is a deterministic Turing machine M , where:*

$$3UNSAT = \{w : M(w, u) = y, \forall \text{ appropriated } u \text{ such that } y \in 0SUM\}$$

when M runs in logarithmic space in the length of w , u is placed on the special read-once tape of M , and u is polynomially bounded by w .

Proof. The input could be a Boolean formula ϕ in $3CNF$ with n variables and m clauses such that each variable is represented by an integer between 1 and n and a positive and a negated literal correspond to the values of k and $-k$, respectively (similar to the DIMACS format: <http://www.satcompetition.org/2009/format-benchmarks2009.html>). We can create a disqualification array A which contains m positive integers between 1 and 3 which represents the position of the literals in the clauses of ϕ from left to right. We read at once

■ **Algorithm 1** Logarithmic space disqualifier with output

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1: /*A valid instance for 3UNSAT with its disqualification*/
2: procedure DISQUALIFIER( $\phi, A$ )
3:   /*Initialize an index*/
4:    $j \leftarrow 0$ 
5:   /* $m$  is the number of clauses in  $\phi$ */
6:   /*Iterate for the elements of the disqualification array  $A$ */
7:   for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $m + 1$  do
8:     if  $i = m + 1$  then
9:       /*There exists an  $m + 1$  element in the array*/
10:      if  $A[i] \neq \text{undefined}$  then
11:        /*Reject the disqualification*/
12:        return "no"
13:      end if
14:      /*Break the for loop*/
15:      break
16:    else if  $A[i] = \text{undefined} \vee A[i] < 1 \vee A[i] > 3$  then
17:      /*Reject the disqualification*/
18:      return "no"
19:    else
20:       $j \leftarrow A[i]$ 
21:    end if
22:    /* $f(i, j)$  is the literal in the position  $j$  in the clause  $c_i$ */
23:    output " ,  $f(i, j)$ "
24:  end for
25: end procedure

```

the elements of the array A and we reject whether this is not an appropriated disqualification: That is when the array A does not contain exactly m elements, or the array A contains a number that is not between 1 and 3. While we read the elements of the array A using the index i , we select from the i^{th} clause in ϕ the single literal such that this one occupies the position that represents the number $A[i]$ within the clause, that is the first, second or third place from left to right. In this way, we output the selected literals that are represented by a positive or negative integer (it is negative in case of a negated variable) just creating another instance C for $0SUM$ where the collection C contains those integers which are the selected literals for each clause in ϕ .

We obtain that all the appropriated array A implies that:

$$\phi \in 3UNSAT \Leftrightarrow (C \in 0SUM \text{ for all appropriated array } A),$$

because of when we obtain an instance $C \notin 0SUM$, then this is equivalent to a satisfying truth assignment in ϕ . Furthermore, we can make this disqualification in logarithmic space such that the array A is placed on the special read-once tape, because we read at once the elements in the array A . Hence, we only need to iterate from the elements of the array A to verify whether the array is an appropriated disqualification and pick the m literals from the Boolean formula ϕ and write those integers to the output tape. We use a function f such that f evaluated in a pair (i, j) outputs the literal in the position j inside of the i^{th} clause just filled with zeroes to the left until we reach a total of $|3 \cdot m|$ bits taking into account the bit-length of integer linked to the literal, where the bit-length of the symbol minus is ignored when we fill the negated literals.

This logarithmic space disqualification with output will be the Algorithm 1. We introduce some constraints in the Algorithm 1 in order to guarantee the theoretical procedure. For example, we assume that a value does not exist in the array A into the cell of a position i when $A[i] = \text{undefined}$. In addition, we immediately reject when the following comparisons:

$$A[i] < 1 \vee A[i] > 3$$

hold at least into one single binary digit. Note that, in the worst case every possible literal in ϕ would have a representation by an integer between $-3 \cdot m$ and $3 \cdot m$ with the exception of 0, where m is the cardinality of the collection C (i.e. when $n = 3 \cdot m$). In this way, we guarantee the output collection C is an appropriated instance of $0SUM$ just using the function f that maps the literals inside of the clauses to numbers with a bit-length equal to $|3 \cdot m|$ where $|\dots|$ is the bit-length function. ◀

► **Theorem 7.** $L = NL$ if and only if $L = NP$.

Proof. This is a direct consequence of Theorems 3, 5 and 6. ◀

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